

EFFECTIVE WAYS TO TEACH ENGLISH TO PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10568490>

Abstract. This article talked about the importance of learning a foreign language in a person's life. And several benefits that being bilingual or multilingual brings to a person were also highlighted. Besides, reasons for increasing demand for learning English and pushing children to study were analyzed. Furthermore, several effective and productive ways to teach pre-school children at home or in kindergartens were introduced and the usefulness of them to a child's development was explained.

Key words: being bilingual, being multilingual, academic and personal development, non-native, monolingual, picture cards, physical activity.

Today English has become one of the world's widely used language and the need to learn English is increasing day by day. Knowing foreign languages, especially, English helps a lot in a number of fields of life, ranging from travelling to international business trades. That is why, people are encouraged to learn English as it is the language of science and education. Why do children need English? Why do parents push children to learn foreign languages at an early age?

A few years ago most parents showed disagreement towards teaching children two languages when they were young as it was believed that children might confuse and have lower academic progress. However, learning more than one language has several advantages for both personal and academic development of a person. First of all, while learning another language, we will be aware of not only the linguistic terms of that language, but also the history, culture of that language, and one new language opens another new culture to broaden one's horizon, to look at the world from a new side. In addition to this, children who speak more than one language success faster in an academic field and have greater achievements as in the process of learning non-native language each part of the brain functions. Besides these personal and academic profits, learning foreign languages has also medical benefit. In fact, people who know more than one language are less likely to catch Alzheimer's disease than people who are monolingual¹.

Nowadays children are guided to learn mostly English by their parents, as English is the world's commonly spoken language. If a person knows English and wants to travel or study abroad, they do not have any difficulties interacting with people and do not face language barrier problems. And also, today employees are required to know English at a beginner level at least due to the fact that English is the language of the Internet, education, tourism and like this. that is why, knowing English is one of the keys to get a well-paid job.

¹ www.teachingenglish.org.uk

Parents are advised to teach children English at early ages but it is clear they will have some problems to get an intended result. Because children lose interest very fast and easily as well as they are curious creatures of humankind. In order to make children interested and stay focused in the process, a number of practical activities have been analyzed by language specialists and several effective ways to teach English to pre-school children are suggested.

1. Songs, dance.

Learning new words with the help of songs rather than repeating them repeatedly is much more effective. As songs have melody, rhythm to keep in mind something fast. Until you sing, dance or shake hands most children never do what is ordered to them. They like imitating what you sing, how you dance. In addition, singing and dancing boost their interest to learn. Cause they tend to get bored and lose delight by revising words monotonously. For example, when the lesson is about body parts, we can use the song “Head, shoulders, knees and toes”. It is a very fun song that children can both uplift their mood by singing and dancing and learn to indicate body parts and their English names. In that case, the role of social media and information and communication technologies is very great. Watching English songs and cartoons make kids more interested and to learn by heart new words quickly as some children are auditory learners that they learn faster by listening.

2. Picture cards.

Some kids are regarded as visual learners. They learn by seeing. It can be movies, pictures and graphs. Moreover, pre-school children do not know how to write letters, in that case using pictures is the best way to introduce new words. For example, when a teacher is conducting a lesson on animals, they can show pictures of different animals so that children imagine in mind, or on a lesson about fruits and vegetables, teachers can use different special objects shaping fruits and vegetables. And they should try to be colorful all the time not to let kids get bored. Furthermore, children may be given to draw the picture of words told by the teacher to revise all words that have been learnt. This also helps children to improve their creativity and drawing skills.

3. Physical activities.

Being physically active assists kids to learn faster. Teachers should conduct the lesson with the help of interactive games. We can teach some words in the game itself. For instance, take “Stand up, sit down” game. We may broaden it by adding, “hands up, hands down, turn right, turn left”. By this, children both learn some verbs and play game to be active. Additionally, kids may do pantomime or imitate the words by actions or sounds which shapes role-playing skills of them. That is to say, one of the children goes out of the room and the teacher tells him/her a word: domestic or wild animals, flowers, objects and so on, and the child enters the room and explain the word to children by acting, pantomime or imitating actions and sounds. Also, we can make children move from one place to another in the room. For instance, if the teacher says the color “red” to find in the room, children should move around the room and locate something that is in red. In such kind of games kinesthetic type of learners are active and get good marks.

Several methods to teach English to children effectively are mentioned above. Parents and teachers can make their kids easily interested by using them. For speaking, more than one language benefits a lot to a person. Firstly, knowing English guarantees higher income in the future, and when one goes abroad for travelling or study it helps much to communicate with

native people there and live without language difficulties so realizing the importance of learning new languages, people are encouraged to be multilingual. It is never too late to learn a new language. However, the earlier a person learns, the easier the process will be since when we are younger, the speed and ease of learning will be much higher than when we are older. Moreover, if we begin to learn a new foreign language as early as possible we are able to have good pronunciation as native speakers.

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